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Variant analysis of COVID-19 genomes

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Abstract

In December 2019, a new coronavirus was discovered in Wuhan, China, which is officially named COVID-19. Within two months of the discovery of the first patient, it has now spread across China and many areas globally. Although the fatality rate is estimated to be low, the number of deaths has already exceeded that of SARS. There have been enormous efforts to contain the virus. Despite the lockdown of the city of Wuhan, the virus has escaped as many people traveled for Lunar New Year. As more patients are infected as time goes by, concerns are that the virus will accumulate more variants and that a virulent strain with stronger toxicity might emerge. Therefore, it is critical to track and characterize them in terms of variants, patient profiles, geographic locations, symptoms, and treatment responses. In this study, we have collected 48 publicly available genomes from 2019-vnCoV infected patients. 80 distinct variants were identified with 43 missense, 21 synonymous, 3 deletion, 11 non-coding and 2 non-coding deletion types. Most common variants were 28144T>C and synonymous 8782C>T in 13 samples which occur for the same samples mostly collected outside of Wuhan. In terms of base pair changes, C>T variants occurred most frequently in 26 distinct variants. All the coding variants were annotated with amino acid information including cleaved non-structured proteins within ORF1ab. Within ORF1ab, samples were bearing more variants in NSP3 domain than other domains. BEAST analysis indicates structured transmission of this strain, with the possibility of multiple introductions into the population.

Introduction

In late 2019, several patients with severe pneumonia were brought into hospitals across the City of Wuhan. The virus causing the pneumonia was sequenced and it was found out that it is a strain of beta-coronavirus and most similarly related to SARS-like BAT coronaviruses bat-SL-CoVZC45 and bat-SL-CoVZXC21 with 88% similarity, 79.5% homology with SARS, and 50% with MERS(1, 2). Since then, more patients showing the symptoms were identified in Wuhan. The Chinese Government decided to lock down the city in an effort to contain the virus. Unfortunately, travels associated with Chinese Lunar New Year aggravated the situation and the virus has spread across China and to many countries. Based on the US CDC, the incubation period of the virus can be as long as 14 days. In addition to that, there appears to be many asymptomatic or mild symptom patients or carriers who might still be transmitting the virus(3).

A study estimated the number of patients to be 75,000 as of January 25, 2020, which far exceeded the Chinese official released number by factor of 10 at that time(4). As a virus transmitted from person to person, as time goes by it inevitably mutates and potentially virulent strains might emerge with high mortality rate. Currently, the mortality rate is estimated lower than that of SARS or MERS(5). Furthermore, potential treatments and vaccines can accelerate the rate that novel mutations fix in the population with treatment resistant substrains. Therefore, tracking of detailed demographic and clinical information as well as substrain information is indispensable to effectively fight against COVID-19.

In this study, variants occurred in 48 genomes as shown in Table 1 were annotated with amino acid changes including non-structured proteins cleaved from ORF1ab.

Results

129 total variants were found and 80 unique variants as shown in Table 2. Among the 48 genomes we analyzed, 10 samples did not exhibit any variants except for missing starts and end base pairs. The distinct variants consist of 43 missense, 21 synonymous, 3 deletion, 11 non-coding and 2 non-coding deletion alleles in **Error! Reference source not found.**. Most common variants were 8782C>T(ORF1ab) and 28144T>C (ORF8) in 13 samples followed by 29095C>T (N) in 5 samples.

The occurrences of 8782C>T and 28144T>C coincide. 29095C>T is found in the subset of them. Both 8782C>T and 29095C>T are synonymous; however, 28144T>C causes amino acid change L84S in ORF8. It is notable that 12 out of 13 of these variant substrains are found outside of Wuhan. Whereas almost all no variants substrain are found from samples collected in Wuhan except for MT039873.

For the 43 missense variants, 30 variants are found in ORF1ab, which is the longest ORF occupying 2/3 of the entire genome. ORF1ab is cleaved into many nonstructural proteins (NSP1-NSP16). Among NSP's, NSP3 has more variants in the analyzed samples.

All three deletions found so far took place in NSP1 of ORF1ab and they are all in-frame deletions. All non-coding deletions are either located in 3'-UTR or 5'-UTR and do not seem to affect functions in major way.

In terms of base changes, most frequently observed one is C>T as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. Since coronaviruses are single strand RNA, we did not combine C>T with G>A mutations. There is strong bias in transition versus transversion ratio as expected(6).

Figure 3 shows a consensus tree from BEAST(7). The resulting tree shows a coalescence center with rapid expansion, except for one side-branch showing relatively slower population growth, which echoes one of the clades marked in beige in Figure 1. This group includes the first traveling family cluster showing transmission without contact with the seafood market (MN938384, MN975262) (8). Further, this cluster is comprised of samples collected in Japan (LC522973, LC522974, LC522975), the first US case (MN985325), the Arizona case (MN997409), other US cases (MN994467 - CA, MT044257 -- IL), a Wuhanese (NMDC60013002-04 = WH04 – Wuhan, not patron at seafood market), a Yunnanese (MT049951) and a Taiwanese patient (MT066175)(1, 9). Another group includes 3 relatively closely related samples (MN994468 – US CA, MT039890 – Korea from traveler to Wuhan, MT007544 – Australia). A slightly earlier branch includes (LC522972 from Japan, and GWHABKG00000001 = WIV02 = MN996527 – Wuhan, no background available). Nearly all of these show coalescence patterns suggestive of more constrained growth, and almost all of them involve long-distance travel, suggesting the possibility that the travelers provided a more constrained growth of effective population size.

Some of the low variant samples identified in Figure 1 appear around the 6-o'clock area of the plot, with some possibility of differential classification tree construction due to differences in pre-processing.

Mutation rates estimated for SARS, MERS, and OC43 show a large range, covering a span of 0.27 to 2.38 substitutions $\times 10^{-3}$ / site / year(10-16). A value range of 0.5- 1×10^{-3} is satisfactory for these preliminary estimates. With a rate of 1×10^{-3} substitutions per site per year, BEAST estimated a median tree height of 1.68 months, 95%CI of 0.92 - 3.64 months, with twice those numbers at the 0.5×10^{-3} rate

Methods

China's National Genomics Data Center (NGDC) has a COVID-19 dedicated page (<https://bigd.big.ac.cn/ncov>), where links to COVID-19 genomes are available. We have downloaded 52 publicly available genomes from Genbank, the NGDC Genome Warehouse, and the National Microbiology Data Center (NMDC) as shown in Table 1. Among 52 genomes, GWHABKP00000001, GWHABKW00000001, NMDC60013002-02, and NMDC60013002-05 were not used for the analysis due to unusually high variants with deletions. Also, MN988713 had ambiguous base and it is converted into appropriate variants. Likewise, NMDC60013002-07 has non-determined bases in 3'-UTR region, which we ignored in the study.

NC_045512 genome sequence was used for reference and genomic coordinate in this study is based on this reference genome. Therefore, genomic coordinates must be adjusted to compare with previous studies, such as Lu et al. It appeared Lu et al. has 25 bp difference prior to the ribosomal slippage site and 24 bp difference after the ribosomal slippage. For instance, 8757C>T in Lu's paper corresponds to our 8782C>T, whereas after the slippage, 24301A>G is 24325A>G.

Each genome was first aligned to NC_045512 using EMBOSS needle with a default gap penalty of 10 and extension penalty of 0.5. Then, differences in comparison with NC_045512 were extracted to create variants table. Based on protein annotations, nucleotide level variants were converted into amino acid codon variants for alignments when its location within a gene was identified.

For ORF1ab, NC_045512 does not have detailed annotations for non-structural proteins. SARS related coronavirus genome NP_828849.2 was used(17). For each non-structured proteins (NSP1-NSP16), we have aligned the protein sequences to NC_045512 ORF1ab protein sequence to create a map of non-structured proteins for COVID-19 ORF1ab. ORF1ab genes has ribosomal slippage site at 13468 near the beginning of NSP12 and caution must be placed for the map. Utilizing the map, we annotated variants in ORF1ab region. Similarly, NSP3 was subdivided into domains: Ubl1, AC(HVR), Mac1(X), Mac2(SUD-N), Mac3(SUD-M), DPUP(SUD-C), Ubl2, PL2pro, betaSM(NAB), G2M, TM1, 3Ecto, TM2, AH1, and Y1+CoV-Y. We used the SARS NSP3 AAP33706.1 aligned with our COVID-19 NSP using EMBOSS needle and coordinates provided by Lei et al(18).

Multiple alignments were performed in NCBI COBALT after blast searches with queries of COVID-19 proteins(19). The particular residues where mutations take places were further investigated for cross species conservations and nature of amino acid changes. The aligned sequence was visualized using alv(20).

EMBOSS Clustal Omega after application of Muscle was used to create the phylogenetic tree in the Figure 1(21, 22). Since many genomes have different start and end points, we have adjusted the length of genomes. Although this approach neglects some variants which occur either in start or end such as NMDC60013002-04 16C>T, the genomes with no variants are gathered in the bottom of the phylogenetic tree.

A preliminary analysis using BEAST generated a consensus view among trees of the viral phylogeny, shown in Figure 3. Sequences were aligned with MAFFT, truncating the first 15 SNPs, and the ragged ends. 1×10^7 MC samples were collected, assuming an HKY mutation model, with a burn-in of 1×10^6 iterations.

Discussion

8782C>T(ORF1ab) and 28144T>C (ORF8) were always found in pair among genomes we analyzed. Multiple alignments with other coronavirus ORF8 sequences suggests that L84 associated with 28144T>C (L84S) is not conserved. Interestingly, many of them were from samples collected in USA and Japan. It is not known whether these substrains have any clinical significance from the information available at this point.

Annotation in these NSP proteins are important since they can be targets of pharmaceutical agents like protease inhibitors. NCBI had released new annotation for orf1ab recently. NSP6 is the only difference and it is considered as a putative protein. Therefore, we retain our NSP annotations, for the time being.

There are 12 distinct variants in NSP3 protein in ORF1ab. NSP3 contains the papain-like protease and is deemed important for SARS virus virulence(23). Variants found in samples originated from Wuhan are located in either TM1 or Y domain which are highly conserved(24). In fact, all the codon I1426, L1417, G1433, G1716, D1761, and N1890, appeared in in GWHABKF000000001, GWHABKJ000000001, GWHABKH000000001, GWHABKM000000001, GWHABKO000000001 and NMDC60013002-01, are conserved among other coronavirus as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Other four variants M84I in MT039890, P153L in MN988713, V267F in MT039888, A358V in LC522973, are at not conserved codons. Whereas, I789V in MT027062 and A921T in MT039888 occurred at highly conserved codons.

Another notable thing about COVID-19 is ORF10 which does not have any similar proteins in a huge repository in NCBI. ORF10 is a short protein or peptide of length 38 residues. This unique protein can be utilized to detect the virus more quickly than PCR based methods. Characterization of ORF10 functions is strongly desired.

BEAST phylogenies give a tantalizing hint of population structuring in the evolution of COVID-19 in the human population. The branches with coalescence patterns most consistent with slow growth are almost all travelers and individuals with no contact with the seafood market. The rest of the growth occurred quite rapidly suggesting near exponential effective population growth. Curiously, not only is the slow-growth branch dominated by travelers, but the COVID-19 lineages appear to be phylogenetically related to each other, suggesting an exposure point for these individuals that is distinct from the rest of the population.

Conclusion

The rapid increase of cases is providing more genomes that may provide some visibility and evidence of population structure, particularly of the possibility of multiple introductions of COVID-19 into the human population. An understanding of the biological reservoirs carrying these viruses, and how the route to market has been bringing them into contact with human populations will be important to understand future risks for novel infections, whether through trade or through recreation and daily work bringing exposure to wild environments.

This study reveals some structure in how the disease spread depending on whether the subjects were travelers or not, with effective population size growth more constrained among the travelers. Further, those travelers all seemed to share lineages not so typical of the rest of the patients which seem to have experienced much more rapid effective population growth. This suggests the exposure points that the travelers were infected through were distinct from those that generated the rapid spread through the Wuhan population.

There is, as of this writing, still no sign of slowdown of the COVID-19 outbreak and number of patients infected appears to be increasing exponentially. This fight against COVID-19 will be a long one until we develop vaccines or effective treatments. It is still an early stage and we have limited knowledge about the virus. However, we believe that sharing information on variants and clinical information will be beneficial. We should continue to be vigilant for emergence of new variants or substrains. As more genomes released in public repositories, the variant analysis will be updated and shared.

List of Abbreviations

COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
AA	Amino Acid
EMBOSS	The European Molecular Biology Open Software Suite
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
CDC	Centers of Disease Control and Prevention
MERS	Middle East Respiratory Syndrome
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
NGDC	National Genomics Data Center
NMDC	National Microbiology Data Center
NSP	Nonstructural Protein
ORF	Open Reading Frame
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
SARS	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome

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Figure 1. A graphical representation of variants found in COVID-19 genomes. Variants are colored depending on the type of mutations (missense, synonymous, non-coding). Gene structure are displayed in the bottom. Phylogenetic tree is generated using EMBOSS Clustal Omega.

Figure 2. Distinct base pair changes observed in COVID-19 genomes

Table 1. List of genomes used in the analysis.

ACCESSION	SAMPLE NAME	DATA SOURCE	LOCATION	COLLECTION DATE
GWHABKF00000001	IPBCAMS-WH-01	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	23-Dec-19
GWHABKG00000001	IPBCAMS-WH-02	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKH00000001	IPBCAMS-WH-03	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKI00000001	IPBCAMS-WH-04	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKJ00000001	IPBCAMS-WH-05	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	1-Jan-20
GWHABKK00000001	WIV02/MN996527	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKL00000001	WIV04/MN996528	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKM00000001	WIV05/MN996529	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKN00000001	WIV06/MN996530	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKO00000001	WIV07/MN996531	Genome Warehouse	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
GWHABKS00000001	20cov-1L	Genome Warehouse	Hangzhou, China	20-Jan-20
NMDC60013002-01	WH01	NMDC	Wuhan, China	26-Dec-19
NMDC60013002-03	WH03	NMDC	Wuhan, China	1-Jan-20
NMDC60013002-04	WH04	NMDC	Wuhan, China	5-Jan-20
NMDC60013002-06	WH19008	NMDC	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
NMDC60013002-07	YS8011	NMDC	Wuhan, China	7-Jan-20
NMDC60013002-08	WH19001	NMDC	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
NMDC60013002-09	WH19004	NMDC	Wuhan, China	1-Jan-20
NMDC60013002-10	WH19005	NMDC	Wuhan, China	30-Dec-19
MN908947	Wuhan-Hu-1	Genbank	Wuhan, China	19-Dec
MN938384	COVID-19_HKU-SZ-002a_2020	Genbank	Shenzhen, China	14-Jan-20
MN975262	COVID-19_HKU-SZ-005b_2020	Genbank	Shenzhen, China	21-Jan-20
MN985325	COVID-19/USA-WA1/2020	Genbank	Snohomish County, Washington, USA	19-Jan-20
MN988668	COVID-19 WHU01	Genbank	Wuhan, China	2-Jan-20
MN988669	COVID-19 WHU02	Genbank	Wuhan, China	2-Jan-20
MN988713	COVID-19/USA-IL1/2020	Genbank	Chicago, Illinois, USA	21-Jan-20
MN994467	COVID-19/USA-CA1/2020	Genbank	Los Angels, California, USA	23-Jan-20
MN994468	COVID-19/USA-CA2/2020	Genbank	Orange County, California, USA	22-Jan-20
MN997409	COVID-19/USA-AZ1/2020	Genbank	Phenix, Arizona, USA	22-Jan-20
MT007544	Australia/VIC01/2020	Genbank	Clayton, Victoria, Australia	25-Jan-20
MT027062	COVID-19/USA-CA3/2020	Genbank	California, USA	29-Jan-20
MT027063	COVID-19/USA-CA4/2020	Genbank	California, USA	29-Jan-20
MT027064	COVID-19/USA-CA5/2020	Genbank	California, USA	29-Jan-20
LC521925	COVID-19/Japan/AI/I-004/2020	Genbank	Japan	20-Jan
MT039887	COVID-19/USA-WI1/2020	Genbank	Wisconsin, USA	31-Jan-20
MT039888	COVID-19/USA-MA1/2020	Genbank	Massachussetts, USA	29-Jan-20
MT039873	HZ-1	Genbank	Hangzhou, China	20-Jan-20
MT039890	SNU01	Genbank	South Korea	20-Jan
MT044257	SARS-CoV-2/IL2/human/2020/USA	Genbank	Illinois, USA	28-Jan-20

MT044258	COVID-19/USA-CA6/2020	Genbank	California, USA	27-Jan-20
LC522972	COVID-19/Japan/KY/V-029/2020	Genbank	Japan	20-Jan
LC522973	COVID-19/Japan/TY/WK-012/2020	Genbank	Japan	20-Jan
LC522974	COVID-19/Japan/TY/WK-501/2020	Genbank	Japan	20-Jan
LC522975	COVID-19/Japan/TY/WK-521/2020	Genbank	Japan	20-Jan
MT066175	SARS-CoV-2/NTU01/2020/TWN	Genbank	Taiwan	31-Jan-20
MT066176	SARS-CoV-2/NTU02/2020/TWN	Genbank	Taiwan	5-Feb-20
MT049951	SARS-CoV-2/Yunnan-01/human/2020/CHN	Genbank	Yunnan, China	17-Jan-20
MT072688	SARSCoV-2/61-TW/human/2020/ NPL	Genbank	Nepal	13-Jan-2020

Table 2. List of variants found in COVID-19 genomes.

ACCESSION	GENOME CHANGE	GENE	AA_CHANGE	TYPE	ORF1 PROTEIN	ORF1 AA_CHANGE
GWHABKF00000001	3778A>G	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
GWHABKF00000001	8388A>G	ORF1ab	N2708S	missense	nsp3-pp1a	N1890S
GWHABKF00000001	8987T>A	ORF1ab	F2908I	missense	nsp4-pp1a	F145I
GWHABKG00000001	104T>A			non-coding		
GWHABKG00000001	111T>C			non-coding		
GWHABKG00000001	112T>G			non-coding		
GWHABKG00000001	119C>G			non-coding		
GWHABKG00000001	120T>C			non-coding		
GWHABKG00000001	124G>A			non-coding		
GWHABKH00000001	6996T>C	ORF1ab	I2244T	missense	nsp3-pp1a	I1426T
GWHABKJ00000001	7866G>T	ORF1ab	G2534V	missense	nsp3-pp1a	G1716V
GWHABKK00000001	21316G>A	ORF1ab	D7018N	missense	nsp16-pp1ab	D220N
GWHABKK00000001	24325A>G	S		synonymous mutation		
GWHABKM00000001	21137A>G	ORF1ab	K6958R	missense	nsp16-pp1ab	K160R
GWHABKM00000001	7016G>A	ORF1ab	G2251S	missense	nsp3-pp1a	G1433S
GWHABKO00000001	8001A>C	ORF1ab	D2579A	missense	nsp3-pp1a	D1761A
GWHABKO00000001	9534C>T	ORF1ab	T3090I	missense	nsp4-pp1a	T327I
LC521925	18512C>T	ORF1ab	P6083L	missense	nsp14-pp1ab	P158L
LC521925	1912C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC521925	359_382del	ORF1ab	G32_L39del	deletion	nsp1-pp1a	G32_L39del
LC522972	11557G>T	ORF1ab	E3764D	missense		
LC522972	15324C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522972	25810C>G	ORF3a	L140V	missense		
LC522972	29303C>T	N	P344S	missense		
LC522973	2662C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522973	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
LC522973	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
LC522973	3792C>T	ORF1ab	A1176V	missense	nsp3-pp1a	A358V
LC522973	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522974	2662C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522974	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
LC522974	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
LC522974	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522975	2662C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
LC522975	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
LC522975	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
LC522975	29705G>T			non-coding		
LC522975	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN938384	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN938384	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
MN938384	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN975262	15607T>C	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN975262	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN975262	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
MN975262	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN975262	9561C>T	ORF1ab	S3099L	missense	nsp4-pp1a	S336L

MN985325	18060C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN985325	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN985325	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN988713	24034C>T	S		synonymous mutation		
MN988713	26729T>C	M		synonymous mutation		
MN988713	28077G>C	ORF8	V62L	missense		
MN988713	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN988713	28854C>T	N	S194L	missense		
MN988713	3177C>T	ORF1ab	P971L	missense	nsp3-pp1a	P153L
MN988713	490T>A	ORF1ab	D75E	missense	nsp1-pp1a	D75E
MN988713	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN994467	1548G>A	ORF1ab	S428N	missense	nsp2-pp1a	S248N
MN994467	24034C>T	S		synonymous mutation		
MN994467	26729T>C	M		synonymous mutation		
MN994467	28077G>C	ORF8	V62L	missense		
MN994467	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN994467	28792A>T	N		synonymous mutation		
MN994467	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MN994468	17000C>T	ORF1ab	T5579I	missense	nsp13-pp1ab	T255I
MN994468	26144G>T	ORF3a	G251V	missense		
MN997409	11083G>T	ORF1ab	L3606F	missense		
MN997409	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MN997409	29095C>T	N		synonymous mutation		
MN997409	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT007544	19065T>C	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT007544	22303T>G	S	S247R	missense		
MT007544	26144G>T	ORF3a	G251V	missense		
MT007544	29750_29758del			non-coding deletion		
MT027062	28854C>T	N	S194L	missense		
MT027062	5084A>G	ORF1ab	I1607V	missense	nsp3-pp1a	I789V
MT027062	614G>A	ORF1ab	A117T	missense	nsp1-pp1a	A117T
MT027063	28854C>T	N	S194L	missense		
MT027063	5084A>G	ORF1ab	I1607V	missense	nsp3-pp1a	I789V
MT027063	614G>A	ORF1ab	A117T	missense	nsp1-pp1a	A117T
MT027064	2091C>T	ORF1ab	T609I	missense	nsp2-pp1a	T429I
MT027064	21707C>T	S	H49Y	missense		
MT039887	17373C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT039888	17423A>G	ORF1ab	Y5720C	missense	nsp13-pp1ab	Y396C
MT039888	24034C>T	S		synonymous mutation		
MT039888	28854C>T	N	S194L	missense		
MT039888	3518G>T	ORF1ab	V1085F	missense	nsp3-pp1a	V267F
MT039888	5480G>A	ORF1ab	A1739T	missense	nsp3-pp1a	A921T
MT039890	12115C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT039890	15597T>C	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT039890	20936C>T	ORF1ab	T6891M	missense	nsp16-pp1ab	T93M
MT039890	22224C>G	S	S221W	missense		
MT039890	25775G>T	ORF3a	W128L	missense		
MT039890	26144G>T	ORF3a	G251V	missense		
MT039890	26354T>A	E	L37H	missense		

MT039890	2971G>T	ORF1ab	M902I	missense	nsp3-pp1a	M84I
MT039890	6031C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT044257	24034C>T	S		synonymous mutation		
MT044257	26729T>C	M		synonymous mutation		
MT044257	28077G>C	ORF8	V62L	missense		
MT044257	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MT044257	3177C>T	ORF1ab	P971L	missense	nsp3-pp1a	P153L
MT044257	490T>A	ORF1ab	D75E	missense	nsp1-pp1a	D75E
MT044257	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT044258	508_522del	ORF1ab	G82_V86del	deletion	nsp1-pp1a	G82_V86del
MT044258	686_694del	ORF1ab	K141_F143del	deletion	nsp1-pp1a	K141_F143del
MT049951	11083G>C	ORF1ab	L3606F	missense		
MT049951	21644T>A	S	Y28N	missense		
MT049951	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MT049951	75C>A			non-coding		
MT049951	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT066175	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
MT066175	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT066176	9034A>G	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
MT066176	9491C>T	ORF1ab	H3076Y	missense	nsp4-pp1a	H313Y
MT072688	24034C>T	S		synonymous mutation		
NMDC60013002-01	11764T>A	ORF1ab	N3833K	missense		
NMDC60013002-01	6968C>A	ORF1ab	L2235I	missense	nsp3-pp1a	L1417I
NMDC60013002-04	16C>T			non-coding		
NMDC60013002-04	28144T>C	ORF8	L84S	missense		
NMDC60013002-04	29854C>T			non-coding		
NMDC60013002-04	29856T>A			non-coding		
NMDC60013002-04	8782C>T	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
NMDC60013002-06	24325A>G	S		synonymous mutation		
NMDC60013002-07	29869del			non-coding deletion		
NMDC60013002-09	27493C>T	ORF7a	P34S	missense		
NMDC60013002-09	28253C>T	ORF8		synonymous mutation		
NMDC60013002-10	20670G>A	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		
NMDC60013002-10	20679G>A	ORF1ab		synonymous mutation		

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